

OPTIMISATION AND AUTOMATION OF WORKFLOWS FROM DATA CAPTURE TO DATA PROCESSING IN ELECTRON MICROSCOPY

*WORK PACKAGE 4: BIG-DATA ELECTRON AND
CORRELATIVE MICROSCOPY FROM
INSTRUMENT TO PUBLICATION*

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Executive summary

Research instruments rarely come “out of the box” with an optimized or even any solutions for automated and high-speed data transfers. Often these solutions are up to the facility or end user (researcher) to develop, and these end up being done on a case-by-case basis.

This work package explores how the automation work at UOW to manage the data from its Cryo Electron Microscope (CryoEM) facility can be extended or reused at other EM, microscopy and bigdata generating instruments. Here we layout details of the workflows developed to move big data and apply insights for other institutions wanting to develop a big data infrastructure for seamless data management.

It is critical to build efficient workflows. UOW has noted that a non-uniform approach to solving this problem hurts productivity, wastes researcher time and can lead to the possibility of data being lost.

This work has demonstrated that:

- A high level (architectural) and uniform (implementation) approach to ALL instruments with high data throughput requirements is essential.
- Some level of scripting on a per site/facility basis will be essential (UOW specific examples are outlined in the report).
- “Default” settings on computers are often not suitable for high-speed transfers – these need to be changed to get better performance.
- Building efficient workflows is as important when dealing with modern high throughput data requirements as fielding high end research instruments. Researchers and facility operators need tools to see end to end visibility of how networks are behaving to make decisions on workflow timing.
- There is an increasing trend for *data sources* i.e., instruments and *data sinks* i.e., storage and compute may not be side by side. Often the computation and long-term storage services may be some distance (interstate or in the cloud) from where data is collected or generated.
- There can be parallel requirements for near real time data processing (e.g., quality control) and longer-term data processing (analysis, generating final maps, structions, decisions). Automation needs to address both these requirements.
- Data image formats and throughputs can change during the life of an instrument – any automation needs to have sufficient flexibility to deal with this. In particular, as instruments may be upgraded, data volumes have the potential to increase significantly. These changes need to be managed and the design must be modular in order to quickly pivot to new hardware, software, and workflow modifications.

- Automating data transfers is likely to be a multi-phase implementation as unexpected behaviours may be identified in early phases, i.e., your automation may actually put significant load on data capture or throughput implementation – leading to worse performance outcomes than expected.
- Automation is key to ensuring data can be managed across multiple parts of a complex workflow – without being lost or corrupted. Where data *is* lost or corrupted it's extremely important to find out ASAP to ensure appropriate remedies can be applied.

1 Introduction

Data movement is the process of migrating data from one location to another within an organisation. At microscopy facilities, data may be moved from its point of capture or generation at an instrument to other locations for the purpose of processing, analysis, storage (short-term or long-term) or archiving. Data may be moved internally within the capture instrument, across a facility or an institution via an internal network, or between facilities or institutions via private networks or the internet. A previous review on data movement at electron microscopy facilities at Australian universities noted that fast, efficient tools and processes to move data from instruments to appropriate locations were critical in order to avoid the risk that data capture at an instrument during an experiment stalls or stops due to the lack of available disk space in the capture device. Indeed, the majority of the facilities interviewed in this review estimated that they generated each close to half a petabyte of data per year and the amount of data generated was rising quickly as data-generation and data-capture technology advanced. Some of the most data-intensive instruments could generate from 100 GB to 2–3 TB of data daily.

Many tasks in data movement are typically manual at microscopy facilities whereas many—if not most—of them could be automated. Automating data movement comprises several advantages. First and foremost, it saves time: instruments scientists and researchers can focus on other activities than the often basic, routine, and repetitive tasks to move data (for example, copy and paste files and folders from one location to another, or clicking “OK” or “next” on a window to start a task). Furthermore, automation minimises the delay between the various steps of a workflow and the risk of human error (for example, missing a step in a workflow or moving the wrong data). Note, there will always be some steps that require some form of human intervention, such as assessing if the data coming from an instrument is of suitable quality to be kept and moved to the next stage of the workflow. In fact, automating tasks to move data ensures that instrument scientists and researchers can focus solely on those steps that depend on their expertise and knowledge.

Various data transfer tools [e.g.: scp, sftp, rsync, rclone, Globus] have been developed to move data, along with programming and scripting languages [e.g.: bash, Python, Java, C++] and schedulers [e.g.: cron, Windows Task Scheduler, systemd] which allow these tools to be incorporated into an automated data-movement workflow.

In this report, approaches for automated workflows for data movement are described. Examples of existing solutions and workflows at a few microscopy facilities are reviewed briefly. Then, taking the Cryogenic Electron Microscopy Facility at the University of Wollongong as a test site, the steps in a data movement workflow that can be automated as well as the underlying work necessary to achieve their automation are presented.

This work was undertaken under the Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale (ACCS) project, in particular under Work Package 4: “Big-data electron and correlative microscopy from instrument to publication”. This report is intended as the conclusion of the work planned for deliverable WP4.2: “Develop optimised and automated workflows for data movement where relevant to minimise human intervention for routine tasks”.

2 Understanding facility data movement

The CryoEM Facility at UOW has a research data workflow that can be broken down into various subflows. These subflows can be individually categorised, prioritised and implemented.

From meetings with Dr James Bower, Director of CryoEM, Dr Simon Brown, CryoEM Operations Manager and Jason Andrade, Research IT Infrastructure Consultant at UOW, we created a data movement map to show the large data transfers that happen throughout the workflow (Figure 1). This allowed us to identify key workflows that can be automated and give each a rating of importance and ease of automation (Table 1).

Some of these have flows direct mappings to each other as noted, and from these, we were able to plan which areas to tackle first.

Figure 1 - Data Movement Map

Table 1 Key steps of the Data Workflow at UOW

Description	Importance	Ease of automation
Capture to Onsite Storage (B)	High	Easy
Onsite Storage to UOW Backup (D)	High	Easy
Onsite Storage to HPC Processing (E)	Medium	Hard
Archive from Backup to Cold Storage	Low	Medium
MRC to TIFF Conversion	High	Medium

3 Existing Automation

The initial intra-site step from Image Capture to Facility Storage (Step B) was already automated prior to the ACCS project. The storage on the capture machine is limited and would fill within a few hours during a data capture run. Data must be moved off to free up space so the capture process can keep running. This initial automation was done by UOW's central IT team.

The central IT team provided a Windows solution to be run on the image capture machine. This was a PowerShell script using a data movement tool called rclone and Windows Task Scheduler was used to run this periodically. This “pushed” the data from the image capture machine to the facility storage server.

Building on the performance improvements identified as part of WP4.4, we realised there was an opportunity to revisit the existing automation for this step. We could convert the current automation to the desired “pull” solution and make both performance and reuse improvements as part of the process. This would allow the new solution to be reused for automating backups to Central Storage (Step D), a process that was manual at this point.

4 Design

We started with the two steps that fell into the “Easy” category. These both had the same design parameters and goal, monitor a folder for new files and transfer them, so we should be able to economise, and create the one solution that can be configured for both steps.

The following are the key factors we were considering when deciding how to implement our new solution.

- Performance - The CryoEM Facility was also looking at how we could improve the near real-time data assessment we were providing to researchers as part of WP4.4. The existing solution fulfilled its goal of preventing the disks in the capture machine from filling up, but performance had never been part of the requirements when this initial solution had been created.
- Pull vs Push - The current 'Push' implementation meant that the CPU load of running the automated transfer was placed on the image capture machine. Switching to a 'Pull' implementation with the automatic transfer running on a dedicated Data Transfer Node (DTN) would shift where this CPU load occurred, reducing the load on the image capture machine.
- Data flow - The data transfer should be between the two remote locations. While the transfer would consume CPU and Network resources on the DTN, we didn't want data landing on the DTN's local drives and adding an extra hop into the transfer path.
- Reuse - The new solution should be flexible enough allow it to be reused for automating backups to Central Storage (Step D), a process that was manual at this point

4.1 Evaluating Scripting Languages

With a list of criteria and plan in mind, a few decisions had to be made around how this was going to be done, and what tools were best suited to this task. We were able to speak with the central IT staff who had created the initial Windows solution. They gave us their blessing to borrow ideas from their solution as the basis for our rewrite and were in agreement with some of the other ideas we'd already sketched out. PowerShell was the logical and native choice for use in a Windows environment. Other than the image capture machine, the rest of the servers in our facility run a Linux operating system. While it is possible to install a port of PowerShell on Linux, using Python was considered the sensible choice. Python was already the top option on our list, so it was reassuring to have this confirmed by others.

- Python is available via the package manager on every nearly every Linux distribution and is typically included as a default part of most Linux installs.
- Python is a "compile at run-time" language, so changes could easily be made to the Python code on the fly during testing, or in the future if extra features were required. This is more complicated with a language that requires code to be compiled into an executable before running. Being more native to Linux than PowerShell, it also meant more support in terms of being able to search up issues and find solutions should we run into any troubles.
- While not a key decision-making point, it was also noted that Python is also widely used within the research community, so should someone else want to modify our code to suit their own unique use case in the future, this could make things much easier for them.

4.2 Evaluating Transfer Tools

The next big decision was which transfer tool to use. The inclination was to go with rclone as per the existing solution. We had already used it for some of our manual data transfers to our remote HPC partner, so were familiar with it. It is multi-platform, available on Windows, Mac and Linux. It supported multiple parallel streams for high throughput. Some of the older existing options had limitations.

- rsync doesn't support multiple parallel streams, and was written in the days of dial-up. It allows resuming in case of a connection dropout, a common issue with dial-up connections. While rsync was fast enough for dial-up connections that were measured in the tens of kilobits per second, the performance of rsync becomes the bottle neck on multi-gigabit connections.
- SFTP allows multiple parallel streams, so could manage better speeds, but still has throughput limitations due to how its encryption is implemented. Many SFTP clients don't support remote to remote transfers.
- Globus requires both endpoints to be internet-connected for communication and authentication with the Globus control servers that orchestrate and manage data the transfer. For security reasons, our Image Capture Machine is not connected to the internet, however we will be keeping an eye on Globus going forwards as it offers tremendous speed over long distances, and automation features are being added. Its recent automation feature "flows" looks promising, and we have been using Globus for data transfers to remote HPC as part of WP4.1.
- rclone is command line based and designed to be easily invoked from automated scripts. It is much more modern and designed with multi-gigabit network links and the Cloud in mind. A key feature of rclone is that it supports many common protocols and APIs to support transfers to and from the multitude of Cloud storage locations, one of which is S3. This would greatly simplify reuse for our backups in Step D, as our centrally provided backup destination is S3,

4.3 Task Schedulers

Moving to a Linux platform meant Windows Task Manager (WTM) was no longer a task scheduler option. Linux has historically used Cron as its task scheduler to fill the same role as WTM fills under Windows, launching tasks at set times or intervals. More recently, "systemd" has been added to Linux. Systemd is a "system and service manager" with features well beyond what we need, however it also has timers and would allow us to configure periodic tasks. This was beneficial in eliminating some edge-case situations present in the original automation solution.

WTM was set to trigger every few minutes, 10 initially, then every 3 as part of the optimisation done in WP4.4. Under "normal" conditions, this wasn't an issue as the task completed quicker than that, however if things took longer than normal, WTM would happily trigger a 2nd instance

of the transfer task compounding performance issues, and potentially leading to errors. This was something we needed to be aware of if the script ever failed, and there was a backlog of images to clear. We would have to manually clean things up before turning the automatic task back on. Systemd keeps track of the tasks its launched and won't launch a 2nd instance if the first one is still running.

We further ensured we wouldn't have multiple instances running by changing the trigger conditions slightly, a feature that systemd allows. Rather than a fixed 3-minute timer as per the WTM settings, systemd timers allow the trigger to be 3 minutes from when the last invocation completed. While this does affect the delay on our near real-time processing, about 3min 20sec between transfers rather than a flat 3min, given we are now confident that we won't end up with multiple instances running concurrently, we can tighten this timing up if desired.

This change also means that if there is a backlog of files to transfer, the next invocation won't happen until 3 minutes after the first one finishes, even if that takes considerably longer. To this point, we've also made use of another feature rclone has that wasn't utilised in the original Windows version and have set a maximum run time of 4 hours, well above the 20 seconds or so it typically takes. If this limit is reach, rclone will stop, and any remaining files will begin transferring when triggered 3 minutes later. While it's hard to imagine what might cause things to take this long, it prevents rclone from getting stuck trying to transfer files for an indefinite length of time. Reaching the 4-hour timeout is flagged as an error by rclone, in turn triggering the "something went wrong" email so an admin can investigate should it ever happen.

4.4 Planned Improvements

The existing automation was great for what it was designed to do, prevent the drives on the image capture machine from filling up. Based on our experiences from running this solution for a few years, and the work we'd been doing as part of WP4.4 to optimise for near real-time assessment, there were quite a few changes and upgrades that we wanted to build into our new solution.

- Move all settings into an easily updated config file. The centrally provided solution had many of its settings hard coded. This had been noticed when we were optimising some of the delays for WP4.4. The source, destination, and who to email if things went wrong were already in an associated config file. Moving all the variables that we might want to change in this or other possible use cases out into the associated would greatly simplify future reusability and performance optimisation.
- Add the option to allow for multiple source and destination locations, each with their own set of transfer parameters. Our facility has multiple microscopes, a 300kV Titan Krios G3 with a K3 detector, a 200kV Talos Arctica with a K2 detector, and a 120kV Tecnai T12 with a Tietz F224 detector. We've decided that in Step B, running multiple copies of this script, one per microscope, would be beneficial as one instance of the script could be stopped if needed without effecting the others, such as during

maintenance on a particular microscope. Backups however (Step D), could be bundled together and achieved via one instance of the script backing up multiple locations.

For these reasons, we have elected to go with Python, rclone and systemd, however we will be monitoring Globus as a potential option in the future.

5 Implementation

Switching from a Push to a Pull approach meant there were some changes that would be required before this could be implemented.

The image capture machine used to connect to a share from our facility storage server and would move the images from its local disk to the network share. For the Pull version, the DTN would sit in the middle, running the transfer. The DTN already had access to the facility storage, however file sharing would need to be configured on the image capture machine to allow the DTN access.

An iterative approach was taken with the implementation of the new solution. Key functionality was added first and tested. Reading settings from the associated config file, performing the transfer, and logging results to file. With the key functionality working, other functions got added, such as emailing the logs to admin staff if something goes wrong, and managing the log files so that logs older than the currently configured time of 2 weeks are cleaned up. This value is one of the many settings added into the config file, so it can easily be adjusted should more or less logs be desired.

We now have three copies of this running, one for our Titan Krios G3 microscope, one for our Talos Arctica microscope, and a third instance of the script to automate our backups (Step D). The Tecnai T-12 is used mostly for training, so data generation is minimal and often discarded given it's 'training data' nature. We've not automated the data transfer from this particular microscope. The backup version has multiple source and destination locations as data from each microscope is saved to its own location. Using automation here has allowed us to move what was a weekly, manual event, to a nightly event that happens on its own. The initial run of this backup, which had a few days' worth of data to catch up on allowed us to confirm that everything happened as expected when the 4-hour limit was reached. The transfer stopped, an email was sent, and the backup was completed the following evening.

6 MRC to TIFF Compression

Recent updates to the software running on the Image Capture machine have allowed the images coming from microscope to be saved as TIFF rather than MRC images. TIFF images are compressed via lossless compression and provide between 3x and 9x space saving depending on the dataset, with an average of just over 5x space saving. This also translates into faster transfer times as the dataset is much smaller. This compression is CPU intensive, and our initial testing was showing stability issues on longer image capture runs. The Image Capture machine runs close to the limits of what its hardware can do, and we noted that the Push script used about 20% of the CPU resources on the Image Capture machine while it was running, a potential cause for the instability. The CPU usage on the Image Capture machine has dropped to about 2% when the Pull script runs, with the DTN picking up the CPU load. Moving this CPU load to a different machine was one of the many reasons for shifting to a pull solution instead of the push one. This didn't solve the instability issues with the TIFF compression option, however it is one less potential cause going forwards.

This has prompted us to look at TIFF compression for our existing data. With hundreds of terabytes of data on both our facility storage server and in backups, having this take up considerably less disk space was a rather attractive carrot. iMod has a "mrc2tif" function as part of its suite of tools, however this takes a single MRC file, compresses it, and outputs a single TIFF file. With hundreds of thousands of images, this was going to be problematic.

To solve this issue, a wrapper script was written that took a folder as its input. It would search through this folder and any subfolders to find all the MRC files. This list would then be split into chunks based on the users' settings, with a few simple sanity checks included based on the number of files, and the CPU of the machine being used to run the compression. On the unlikely chance that the dataset folder only contained a few MRC files, there was no way to split this into more chunks than there were files. Likewise, there was no benefit in splitting the list into more chunks than there were CPU cores. Each chunk was then processed in parallel, with iMod's "mrc2tif" function being automatically passed images one after the other. This has allowed us to easily compress entire data sets. So far, over 100TB, and 100,000 files have already compressed to just over 20TB, a considerable space saving.

Testing has also been done to confirm that our main pieces of image processing software, cryoSPARC and Relion function just as well with TIFF files as they have with the previous MRC files, and that the compression is indeed lossless and doesn't affect the analysis results.

Further software updates from the vendor have solved the stability issue, and now allow us to perform the compression at point of capture, eliminating a step of our workflow. The previous work for automating the conversion of entire data sets from MRC to TIFF will still be useful for reducing backup storage space for previously captured datasets, a task that is still ongoing.

7 Results

The “pull” solution is now in ‘production’ and is working much better than expected. While running as a “push” from Windows, the transfers to our facility storage server would happen at about 1.5Gbit/s and take about 60% of the time between each triggering of the script. Running as a “pull” from the DTN, we’re now seeing about 6Gbit/s, and the transfer is taking about 10-12% of the time. This is using the same transfer tool, rclone, along with the same source, destination, and 10Gbit/s network link on the Image Capture PC, the network bottleneck in our system.

There was extensive network tuning and testing performed on our DTN in conjunction with Chris Myers from AARNet as part of WP4.1 to improve transfer speeds when sending large data sets to remote HCP via Globus. This has helped the pull solution produces superior performance.

We have been pleasantly pleased with the drop in CPU usage on the image capture machine which has resulted from the “pull” rather than “push” script. To avoid creating a “Disk IO” issue that could cause problems saving the images coming from the microscope in the first place, we’ve lowered the settings on the DTN, running 2 parallel threads rather than the 8 threads that the Windows version used to run.

8 Conclusion

CryoEM/EM and big data facilities should be built with plenty of network bandwidth to spare. However, this is not always the case. This means that pull solutions should be suitable well into the future, even with future upgrades to better quality, higher frame rate detectors.

UOW’s recent upgrade from a K2 to K3 detector has seen about a four-fold increase in the amount of data being generated from a capture run due to the increased size of the cameras’ detector, as well as the much higher frame rate being captured (in excess of 1500 frames per second of raw data, from the previous 500 frames per second on the K2). This has for the most part, been offset with the MRC to TIFF compression, so that the end data volume has not drastically expanded – but it’s still a measurably larger amount and is being produced much more quickly.

With the current 10-12% “mark-space” ratio between *transfer* time and *idle* time moving images from the capture machine to facility storage, there is sufficient time available that the current solutions for moving data would continue to work and could scale up appropriately (another four- or five-fold future increase in data rates will be manageable) without needing to change the fundamental architecture and implementation.

For future work, we will look at mapping a network share to the capture machine, and have the images save directly to our facility storage, getting rid of the transfer script entirely. This is not currently supported by the vendor. As part of working with the vendor (a challenging task), there will also need to be technical validation work required before we could move to this approach.

Currently, if the network dropped out or some other issue occurred that prevented images from being transferred to the facility storage server, the capture run will continue as images are saved locally before being transferred. These images could potentially be lost if the default save location was changed to a network location.

In summary, We’ve developed, as part of the ACCS, a data management architecture that addresses the need for the automated movement of Big Data within a modular workflow environment (including transfer, storage, and processing), that is efficient, simple to use and requires minimal upkeep by IT professionals.

9 Contributorship

Joshua Silver (UOW)

Jason Andrade (UOW)

Dr Simon Brown (UOW)

Dr James Bouwer (UOW)

10 Acknowledgements

Dr David Poger (Microscopy Australia)

Jay van Schyndel (Monash)

Chris Myers (AARNet)

11 Glossary

ACCS:	Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale
CryoEM:	Cryogenic Electron Microscopy
DTN:	Data Transfer Node. A server with the specific role of moving data from one location to another.
MRC:	Common image file format used for CryoEM images developed by the UK Medical Research Council Laboratory of Molecular Biology
SFTP:	Secure File Transport Protocol. A protocol for transferring files between computers that includes encryption.
TIFF:	Tag Image File Format. Common image file format used for CryoEM images with lossless compression.
UOW:	University of Wollongong
WTM:	Windows Task Manager. Built-in task scheduler for the Windows operating system.

12 References

<https://github.com/Characterisation-Virtual-Laboratory/Data-Movement-Automation>
<https://github.com/Characterisation-Virtual-Laboratory/MRC-to-TIFF-Conversion>